

Preparation of novel lithiated high-entropy spinel-type oxyhalides and their electrochemical performance in Li-ion batteries

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Olena Porodko^a, Ladislav Kavan^b, Martin Fabián^{a*}, Barbora Pitňa Lásková^b, Vladimír Šepelák^{a,c}, Hristo Kolev^d, Klebson Lucenildo da Silva^{c,e}, Maksym Lisnichuk^f and Markéta Zukalová^{b*}

Compositionally complex doping of spinel oxides toward high entropy oxides is expected to enhance their electrochemical performance substantially. We successfully prepared high-entropy compounds, i.e., the oxide $(\text{Zn}_{0.25}\text{Mg}_{0.25}\text{Co}_{0.25}\text{Cu}_{0.25})\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (HEOFe), lithiated oxyfluoride $\text{Li}_{0.5}(\text{Zn}_{0.25}\text{Mg}_{0.25}\text{Co}_{0.25}\text{Cu}_{0.25})_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_{3.5}\text{F}_{0.5}$ (LiHEOFeF), and lithiated oxychloride $\text{Li}_{0.5}(\text{Zn}_{0.25}\text{Mg}_{0.25}\text{Co}_{0.25}\text{Cu}_{0.25})_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_{3.5}\text{Cl}_{0.5}$ (LiHEOFeCl) with spinel-based cubic structure by ball milling and subsequent heat treatment. The products exhibit particles with sizes from 50 to 200 nm with a homogeneous atomic distribution. The average elemental composition of the samples is close to the nominal value. ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer spectroscopy revealed that incorporating Li and F or Cl and forming oxygen defects do not influence the redistribution of Fe³⁺ cations over the spinel lattice sites and results in their preferred octahedral coordination. Electrochemical measurements carried out using the 2032-coin cells with the Li-metal anode have shown voltammetric charge capacities of 450, 694, and 593 mAh g⁻¹ for HEOFe, LiHEOFeCl, and LiHEOFeF, respectively. The best electrochemical performance of LiHEOFeCl was ascribed to its smallest particle size. Galvanostatic chronopotentiometry at 1 C rate confirmed high initial charge capacities for all the samples but galvanostatic curves exhibited a capacity decay over 100 charging/discharging cycles. Raman spectroelectrochemistry measured on the LiHEOFeF sample proved the reversibility of the electrochemical process for initial charging/discharging cycles. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy revealed the lowest initial charge transfer resistance for LiHEOFeCl and its gradual decrease both for LiHEOFeCl and LiHEOFeF during galvanostatic cycling, whereas the charge transfer resistance of HEOFe slightly increases over 100 galvanostatic cycles due to different mechanism of the electrochemical reduction.

1 Introduction

The current technological boom, digitalization, and the development of portable devices supporting online services go hand in hand with the high demand for high-capacity batteries with cycling stability enabling fast charging/discharging. Regardless of various newly developed battery systems, Li-ion batteries remain an essential energy storage system for the majority of applications. However, the charge capacity of electrode materials used for classical Li-ion batteries is limited to ca. 180 mAh g⁻¹. The intercalation anodes are limited by the capacity of graphite, (372 mAh g⁻¹ for LiC₆). To satisfy progress in advanced rechargeable lithium-ion batteries, a significant effort has been devoted to exploring electrode materials with optimal electrochemical properties. The novel concept of compositionally complex doping led to high-entropy

compounds¹. This allows the compositional variability needed to design new materials for next-generation batteries². These compounds comprise the incorporation of multiple metal cations into single-phase crystal structures. Interactions among the various metal cations lead to unique electrochemical³ and magnetic⁴ properties. This concept was originally developed for high-entropy alloys (HEAs) and the role, that entropy plays in the phase stability of these compounds, can be understood in terms of the Gibbs free energy of mixing (ΔG_{mix})^{2, 5}

$$\Delta G_{\text{mix}} = \Delta H_{\text{mix}} - T\Delta S_{\text{mix}} \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_{mix} is the mixing enthalpy, ΔS_{mix} is the mixing entropy, and T is the absolute temperature. If the $T\Delta S_{\text{mix}}$ dominates the enthalpy term (ΔH_{mix}), the overall ΔG_{mix} becomes negative and the entropy stabilization is established⁵. The mixing entropy (ΔS_{mix}) includes many entropic terms; however, the configurational entropy (ΔS_{conf}) is usually dominant^{2, 5}. Another definition considers several elements, i.e. HEAs are formed by mixing equal or relatively large proportions of (usually) five or more elements⁶. Like HEAs, entropy-based definitions have been proposed for high-entropy oxides (HEOs), where the configurational entropy from both cations and anions is considered^{7, 8}. Typically, the entropy contribution of O²⁻ is zero, but the presence of oxygen vacancies or other anions (e.g., F⁻) can contribute to the system's entropy⁷. HEOs with spinel structure are suitable anode components in Li-ion batteries due to their high-rate capability and three-dimensional transport of lithium ions^{9, 10}. In this context, several papers reported on the electrochemical properties of HEOs with spinel structure of

^a Institute of Geotechnics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Watsonova 45, 040 01, Košice, Slovak Republic

^b J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry, Czech Acad. Sci., Dolejškova 3, CZ-18223, Prague 8, Czech Republic

^c Institute of Nanotechnology, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany

^d Institute of Catalysis, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev St., Bldg. 11, Sofia, 1113, Bulgaria

^e Department of Physics, State University of Maringá, Av. Colombo 5790, 87020-900 Maringá, Brazil

^f Institute of Physics, Pavol Jozef Šafárik University, Park Angelinum 9, 04154 Košice, Slovakia

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various compositions and morphologies, (see, Refs.^{11–18}, and references therein). The stabilization effect of entropy brings significant benefits for the storage capacity retention of high entropy compounds and greatly improves their cycling stability. Additionally, the electrochemical behavior of high entropy compounds depends on each of the metal cations present, thus providing the opportunity to tailor the electrochemical properties by simply changing the composition³. To increase the discharge capacity, Lökçü et al.¹⁹ reported the synthesis of lithium-containing high-entropy (MgCoNiZn)_{1-x}Li_xO oxides. Subsequently, a variety of HEOs with incorporated lithium have been introduced. Duan et al.²⁰ reported on anode material (FeCoNiCrMnXLi)₃O₄ where X = Cu, Mg, or Zn. Their (FeCoNiCrMnZnLi)₃O₄ exhibited specific discharge capacities of 695, 577, 460, 336, 250, and 173 mAh g⁻¹ at 50 mA g⁻¹, 100 mA g⁻¹, 200 mA g⁻¹, 500 mA g⁻¹, 1000 mA g⁻¹ and 2000 mA g⁻¹, respectively. In a similar work²¹, the (CoNiZnFeMnLi)₃O₄ provided an initial specific discharge capacity of 1104.3 mAh g⁻¹, good cycle stability (84% capacity retention after 100 cycles at 100 mA g⁻¹), and rate performance of 293 mAh·g⁻¹ at 2000 mA g⁻¹. Ma et al.²² synthesized (FeMgNiCrMnLi)₃O₄ using the solution combustion method combined with ball milling. This material showed a reversible discharge capacity of 850.7 mAh g⁻¹ after 200 cycles at 2.0 A g⁻¹.

In our recent work²³, we reported a novel lithiated high-entropy oxychloride Li_{0.5}(Zn_{0.25}Mg_{0.25}Co_{0.25}Cu_{0.25})_{0.5}Fe₂O_{3.5}Cl_{0.5} (LiHEOFel) as an additive increasing the stability of a sulfur cathode in Li-sulfur batteries. A considerable effect of the LiHEOFel material was assigned to its excellent structural and electrochemical stability within the operating window of the Li-sulfur battery, where it had no inherent electrochemical activity and acted solely as an electrocatalyst. The charge capacity of LiHEOFel (evaluated by cyclic voltammetry in the potential window of 0.65/3.0 V vs. Li⁺/Li at the scan rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹) reached 648 mAh g⁻¹. Since this value exceeds almost four times the charge capacities of the state-of-the-art oxide anodes for Li-ion batteries and almost twice the capacity of a graphite anode, it is challenging to carry out a more detailed electrochemical study completed with galvanostatic charging/discharging, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, and structural analysis. In addition, the same study is carried out for the parent (Zn_{0.25}Mg_{0.25}Co_{0.25}Cu_{0.25})Fe₂O₄ (HEOFel) and its lithium-containing fluorinated homologue Li_{0.5}(Zn_{0.25}Mg_{0.25}Co_{0.25}Cu_{0.25})_{0.5}Fe₂O_{3.5}F_{0.5} (LiHEOFef).

The objective of the present study is to establish the synthetic route of lithiated HEO oxides and oxyhalides and characterize their structure, composition, morphology, and crystallite size distribution by a combination of X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD), Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), and Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM). To determine atomic structure on the local level, ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer spectroscopy is employed to provide the local environment of Fe nuclei. Moreover, valence states of particular elements are investigated via X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) to

examine their detailed electrochemical properties, together with their electrochemical performances.

2 Experimental

2.1 Sample preparation

The (Zn_{0.25}Mg_{0.25}Co_{0.25}Cu_{0.25})Fe₂O₄ (HEOFel), Li_{0.5}(Zn_{0.25}Mg_{0.25}Co_{0.25}Cu_{0.25})_{0.5}Fe₂O_{3.5}F_{0.5} (LiHEOFef) and Li_{0.5}(Zn_{0.25}Mg_{0.25}Co_{0.25}Cu_{0.25})_{0.5}Fe₂O_{3.5}Cl_{0.5} (LiHEOFel) were prepared by combination of ball milling and heat treatment. In the first step, a stoichiometric ratio of precursors: zinc oxide (ZnO, 99.99% Aldrich), copper oxide (CuO, 99.99% Acros Organics), magnesium oxide (MgO, 99.99%, Acros Organics), iron oxide (α-Fe₂O₃, 99.9%; Alfa Aesar) and lithium chloride (LiCl, 98%, Acros Organics) or lithium fluoride (LiF, 99.9 %, Acros Organics) were used. The cobalt oxide CoO precursor was prepared by thermal decomposition of cobalt hydroxide (Co(OH)₂, 95% Acros Organics) at 180 °C in a vacuum. The mixture of precursors (see Eqs 2-4) was milled at 600 rpm for 390 minutes in a planetary ball mill Pulverisette 7 premium line (Fritsch). A milling chamber (80 cm³ in volume) and balls (10 mm in diameter) made of tungsten carbide (WC) were used. The ball-to-powder weight ratio was 30:1. Milling was carried out in an argon atmosphere.

In the second step, the mechanically activated mixtures were calcined at 600°C in an argon atmosphere for 2 h.

2.2 Structure determination

XRPD patterns were collected using a D8 Advance diffractometer (Bruker) operating with Cu Kα radiation in the Bragg-Brentano configuration. The generator was set up at 40 kV and 40 mA and data were recorded in the range of 20 to 80° 2θ. The ICSD²⁴ database was applied for the assignment of phases. Lattice parameters were determined by the Le Bail method in the space group *Fd* $\bar{3}$ *m* using the FullProf program²⁵ with the application of regular pseudo-Voigt function parameters.

Microstructure and morphology of the synthesized powders were investigated by (S)TEM (JEOL JEM -2100F), coupled with the Energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDS) (Oxford

Instruments). The sample was crushed in a mortar, dispersed in ethanol, and fixed on a copper-supported carbon grid. ImageJ software²⁶ was used to evaluate the particle size distribution from the (S)TEM micrographs.

The elemental composition was investigated by atomic absorption spectrometry AAS (Varian 240RS/240Z). Before the AAS measurement, the powdered samples were dissolved in aqua regia, filtered, and diluted.

The ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer spectra were measured in transmission geometry at room temperature. The ⁵⁷Co isotope in the Rh matrix was used as the γ -ray source. Mössbauer data were fitted using the spectral analysis software "Recoil"²⁷. The Voigt-based fitting method was applied for all spectra. The experimental data were analyzed using a fitting procedure that considers hyperfine field distribution for the octahedrally coordinated ferric cations, Fe³⁺[O_h]. This results in the asymmetric broadening of the Fe³⁺[O_h] subspectrum arising from the different possible nearest-neighbor (T_d)-site configurations via supertransfer mechanism in magnetic spinels²⁸. In contrast, the Fe³⁺(T_d) subspectrum reflects the presence of a narrower field distribution in agreement with the usually smaller (T_d)-site supertransferred hyperfine field²⁹. The derived isomer shifts (IS) are normalized to the IS of α -Fe.

XPS was performed on (ESCALAB MkII, VG Scientific, now Thermo Fisher Scientific) to analyze the elemental composition of the surface and oxidation states of the metal ions. Measurements were conducted at room temperature under 5 \times 10⁻⁹ mbar. A twin anode MgK α /AlK α X-ray source was used with excitation energies of 1253.6/1486.6 eV, respectively. The spectra were recorded at the total instrumental resolution (as it was measured with the FWHM of Ag3d_{5/2} photoemission line) of 1.06 and 1.18 eV for MgK α and AlK α excitation sources, respectively. The binding energies of all the elements were calibrated relative to C 1s at 285.0 eV. The processing of the measured spectra included the subtraction of X-ray satellites and a Shirley-type background³⁰. The peak positions and areas were determined by a symmetrical Voigt-based curve fitting.

2.3 Electrode preparation

The respective electrode material (HEOFe, LiHEOFeCl, or LiHEOFeF) was mixed with a conductive carbon black C65 (Timcal), and a 2 % aqueous solution of carboxymethylcellulose (CMC from Sigma). The mass ratio of the HEO-containing active material to C65 and CMC was 7:2:1. The mixture was then diluted with deionized water to a consistency of viscous paste and coated by doctor-blading on Al foil. After drying in air at ambient temperature and subsequently at 100 °C in a vacuum overnight, the coated Al foil was cut into disc electrodes of 15 mm in diameter. The electrodes were stored in a glove box with an argon atmosphere.

2.4 Coin cells preparation

Coin cells were assembled with a cathode described above, a Li-foil anode (14 mm in diameter), a glass microfiber separator (Whatman), and 20 μ L of electrolyte solution. The electrolyte solution consisted of 1 M LiPF₆ in ethylene carbonate/dimethyl carbonate (1:1 by volume). Electrolyte solutions contained 8-12 ppm H₂O as determined by Karl Fischer coulometric titration (Mettler Toledo). Electrolytes and solvents were of standard quality (p.a. or electrochemical grade) purchased from Aldrich or Merck. The electrolyte solution for Raman spectroelectrochemical measurement consisted of 1M LiClO₄ in ethylene carbonate/dimethyl carbonate (1:1 by volume). The scheme S1 (Supporting Info) depicts the coin cell for Raman spectroelectrochemistry. The cell was equipped with a glass window to the cathode for in situ spectral measurement.

2.5 Electrochemical characterization

Cyclic voltammetry measurements were carried out with Autolab 302N potentiostat (Metrohm) controlled by Nova SW in a potential window of 0.65 V/3.0 V vs. Li⁺/Li with a scan rate of 50, 20, 10, 5, 2, 1, 0.5, 0.2, and 0.1 mV s⁻¹. All potentials in this study are referred to the Li⁺/Li electrode. Galvanostatic chronopotentiometry at 1C was measured in the 2032 coin-type test cells by the Neware Battery Testing System controlled by BTS 7.6 SW. Electrochemical impedance spectra (EIS) of the particular coin cell were measured after cyclic voltammetry measurements, then after the 50th and 100th galvanostatic cycle by the FRA2 module of Autolab 302N. EIS was investigated over a frequency range from 100 kHz to 0.1 Hz (modulation amplitude 10 mV) at 2.4 V vs. Li⁺/Li (which is near the open-circuit potential). Before each EIS measurement, the potential was equilibrated at 2.4 V for 1 min. Spectra were evaluated using the Zview 4.0 (Scribner) software by fitting to a Randles-type circuit, in which *R*_s is the serial resistance, and *R*_{CT} (the charge-transfer resistance) is parallel to the constant phase element (*CPE*) to account for non-ideal capacitive behavior of the cell. The circuit is completed by the Warburg impedance *Z*_w element for modeling the mass transport effects at lower frequencies^{31, 32}. However, in contrast to the cited works, in which the impedances were normalized to the electrode area, we present now the spectra normalized to the mass of active electrode material³³. Alternative normalization [to the physical (BET) areas] will give a similar result – the actual surface areas are all near 4 m² g⁻¹ (Ref.²³). The Raman spectra were measured on a MicroRaman system (LabRAM HR spectrometer, Horiba Jobin–Yvon) interfaced to an Olympus BX microscope. The spectra were excited by a He–Ne laser, 633 nm. The Raman spectrometer was calibrated using the F_{1g} line of Si at 520.2 cm⁻¹. The in-situ Raman spectra were measured during chronoamperometry in a quasi-equilibrium state, which was attained after 2 min of arresting the electrode potential at the selected value. Chronoamperometry was carried out with Autolab PGSTAT30 apparatus controlled by Nova SW in the potential window of 3.0 V - 0.7 V vs. Li⁺/Li.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Structural and morphological properties

Figure 1 shows the XRPD patterns of the as-prepared samples. They confirmed the spinel-based phase with a cubic structure ($Fd\bar{3}m$), without detectable impurities. A slight shift of the diffraction peaks for LiHEOFeF and LiHEOFeCl to the higher angular positions is observed (Figure 1, inset). This shift indicates the incorporation of lithium and fluoride/chloride ions into the spinel lattice. As further summarized in Table 1, the calculated lattice parameters decrease with the incorporation of lithium and halide ions, which is reasonable considering the difference in the ionic radii of the particular elements³⁴. The mean crystallite sizes of the studied samples, determined from Scherrer's equation, are from 50 to 70 nm. The morphology and particle size distribution were further investigated by (S)TEM. Figure 2 shows representative micrographs of the synthesized samples. They consist of agglomerated particles with a size distribution ranging from 100 to 200 nm, except for LiHEOFeF characterized by bigger particles. Approximately 100 particles were analyzed to determine the average crystallite size D (listed in Table 1). The average particle size determined by (S)TEM analysis is higher than that from XRPD. It is attributed to the agglomeration of particles. Moreover, the HR-TEM images show lattice fringes characteristic for the particular crystallographic planes (twenty atomic planes were analyzed to determine the average value). The observed values are in good agreement with those determined from XRPD data according to the following formula:

$$1/d_{hkl}^2 = (h^2 + k^2 + l^2)/a^2 \quad (5)$$

where hkl are Müller indices, and a is the lattice parameter.

EDS mapping of the particular elements Zn, Mg, Cu, Co, Fe, O, F, and Cl reveals their homogeneous distribution (Figure 3). Contamination attributed to the abrasion during the milling process was at the detection limit of EDS (0.4 at. % W). Even though, according to our recent experience³⁰, the low concentration of tungsten has an insignificant effect on the electrochemical properties of oxide-based anodes. As listed in Table 2, the final chemical composition of the synthesized spinels is quasi-equimolar and the average elemental composition determined by AAS is close to the nominal composition.

Figure 1. XRPD patterns of HEOFe, LiHEOFeF, and LiHEOFeCl. Inset is a zoomed image to accent the shift of diffraction peaks by the structure modification. Vertical lines are guides to the eye.

Table 1. The lattice parameter (a), interplanar distance (d), and average crystallite size (D) for HEOFe, LiHEOFeF, and LiHEOFeCl

Sample	Lattice parameter, a (Å)	Interplanar distance, d observed (Å)	Interplanar distance, d calculated (Å)	Crystallite size, D XRD (nm)	Crystallite size, D TEM (nm)
HEOFe	8.4008(9)	2.8 for ($hkl = 003$)	2.8 for ($hkl = 003$)	54	140
LiHEOFeF	8.3662(1)	4.7 for ($hkl = 111$)	4.8 for ($hkl = 111$)	53	214
LiHEOFeCl	8.3690(4)	2.8 for ($hkl = 222$)	2.8 for ($hkl = 222$)	65	155

To address the local structural arrangement of the as-prepared materials, the samples were investigated by ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer

Figure 2. (S)TEM and HR-TEM micrographs of a) HEOFe, b) LiHEOFef, and c) LiHEOFec synthesized samples. Insets show the particle size distribution. Interplanar distances, d , correspond to those determined by Eq. 5, d) Idealized spinel structure of investigated samples. Particular crystal planes for HEOFe (003), LiHEOFef (111) and LiHEOFec (222) are highlighted.

spectroscopy. This method provides information on the chemical (valence) and magnetic states of the constituent iron ions including their local coordination and oxygen polyhedral distortions³⁵. It is known that spinel ferrites with the general formula $M1M2_2O_4$ ($M1$ and $M2$ are divalent and trivalent metal cations, respectively) exhibit complex disordering phenomena involving the redistribution of cations over the sites of tetrahedral (T_d) and octahedral [O_h] coordination provided by the spinel structure^{36–39}. To emphasize the site occupancy at the atomic level, the structural formula of these materials may be written as $(M1_{1-\lambda}M2_\lambda)[M1_\lambda M2_{2-\lambda}]O_4$, where the parentheses and square brackets denote (T_d) and [O_h] sites, respectively. The symbol λ represents the so-called degree of inversion defined

Figure 3. (S)TEM micrograph of synthesized (a) HEOFe, (b) LiHEOFef, and (c) LiHEOFec samples with the corresponding elemental maps determined by EDS.

as the fraction of the (T_d) sites occupied by trivalent ($M2^{3+}$) cations. It varies from $\lambda = 0$ (normal spinel) to $\lambda = 1$ (fully inverse spinel). The value of $\lambda = 2/3$ corresponds to the random arrangement of cations. A non-equilibrium cation distribution has been evidenced in spinels prepared by various synthesis routes^{40–44}.

Figure 4 shows the room-temperature ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectra of HEOFe, LiHEOFef, and LiHEOFec. The spectra of all investigated samples are well-fitted using two overlapping sextets corresponding to Fe^{3+} ions located on both (T_d) and [O_h] sites provided by the spinel ferrite structure. Table 3 presents the hyperfine parameters of (T_d)- and [O_h]-site ferric ions in the investigated materials. From the intensities of spectral components, it is revealed that Fe^{3+} cations in the HEOFe sample incline to the random distribution over tetrahedral and octahedral positions ($I(T_d)/I(O_h) \sim 33/67$). As it is evident from the quantitative analysis of ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectra, the presence of Li and F or Cl ions in the structures of the LiHEOFef and LiHEOFec does not influence the redistribution of Fe^{3+} cations and results in their preferred octahedral coordination ($I(T_d)/I(O_h) \sim 34/66$ for LiHEOFef and $I(T_d)/I(O_h) \sim 34/66$ for LiHEOFec; see Table 3). It should be emphasized that the presented values of the intensities of Mössbauer subspectra reflect only the distribution of Fe^{3+} . The estimation of the degree of inversion for the HEOFe, LiHEOFef, and LiHEOFec samples is not possible, because the distribution of other constituent cations among (T_d) and [O_h] sites in the spinel structures is unknown.

Figures 5a–h show the XPS spectra (measured with the AlK α excitation, see Experimental) of Zn2p, Mg1s, Co2p_{1/2}, Cu2p_{3/2}, Fe2p, O1s, F1s, and Cl2p for the samples HEOFe, LiHEOFef, and LiHEOFec, respectively. Figure 5a compares the Zn2p energy range of the samples. For all three samples, the shape of the line is identical with a binding energy of 1021.2 eV, indicating a Zn oxidation state of Zn^{2+} ^{45, 46}. Figure 5b presents the Mg1s photoelectron lines. Dashed lines indicate the positions of photoemission lines of Mg^0 (1303.0 eV) and Mg^{2+} (1304.3 eV) reported in the literature⁴⁷. Variations in the line shape suggest Mg-F bonding in LiHEOFef, and possible Mg-O and Mg-Mg bonding in all three samples. In LiHEOFec, the line shape is influenced by the Auger peak of chlorine (ClKMM).

Table 2.

Elemental composition of HEOFe, LiHOFef, and LiHOFefCl samples represented by the M/Fe atomic ratios determined by AAS.

HEOFe	Zn/Fe	Mg/Fe	Co/Fe	Cu/Fe	Li/Fe
<i>expected</i>	0.1250	0.1250	0.1250	0.1250	–
<i>measured</i>	0.1475	0.1350	0.1375	0.1238	–
LiHOFef					
<i>expected</i>	0.0625	0.0625	0.0625	0.0625	0.2500
<i>measured</i>	0.0770	0.0702	0.0690	0.0616	0.1931
LiHOFefCl					
<i>expected</i>	0.0625	0.0625	0.0625	0.0625	0.2500
<i>measured</i>	0.0575	0.0560	0.0628	0.0538	0.2292

Table 3.

Hyperfine parameters (*IS*: isomer shift, B_{hf} : the average magnetic hyperfine field, *I*: relative intensity of the spectral component) obtained by fitting the room-temperature ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectra of the HEOFe, LiHOFef, and LiHOFefCl samples.

Sample	Spectral component	<i>IS</i> (mm/s)	B_{hf} (T)	<i>I</i> (%)
HEOFe	(T _d) (dark blue)	0.12(3)	45.9(1)	32.9(5)
	[O _h] (light blue)	0.26(4)	41.1(9)	67.1(5)
LiHOFef	(T _d) (dark blue)	0.15(6)	46.3(1)	34.4(6)
	[O _h] (light blue)	0.18(8)	48.9(4)	65.6(3)
LiHOFefCl	(T _d) (dark blue)	0.16(8)	40.2(8)	33.5(1)
	[O _h] (light blue)	0.19(4)	42.2(8)	66.5(1)

Figure 3. The room-temperature ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectra of a) HEOFe, b) LiHOFef, and c) LiHOFefCl. The dark blue and light blue spectra correspond to tetrahedrally (T_d) and octahedrally [O_h] coordinated iron cations, respectively

Figure 4. High-resolution XPS spectra of the HEOFe, LiHFeF, and LiHFeCl compounds showing the signals corresponding to (a) Zn2p, (b) Mg1s, (c) Co2p_{1/2}, (d) Cu2p_{3/2}, (e) Fe2p, (f) O1s, (g) F1s and (h) Cl2p

The Co2p_{1/2} spectra in Figure 5c confirm the presence of Co²⁺ with a peak at 796.5 eV binding energy, accompanied by an intense 3d→4s “shake-up” satellite at 802.5 eV^{45, 48}. Figure 5d shows the Cu2p_{3/2} signal. The satellite structure in the 938–946 eV range indicates a Cu oxidation state of Cu²⁺^{45, 49, 50}. Curve fitting suggests Cu⁺/Cu²⁺ ratios of 0.4 and 4.1 for HEOFe and LiHFeF, respectively. The noisy spectrum of LiHFeCl complicates the analysis, but a Cu²⁺ oxidation state is likely. Thus, the lithiated samples stabilize Cu⁺ ions on the surface, whereas Cu²⁺ predominates in HEOFe. It is interesting to note two different chemical shifts for Cu²⁺. The Fe2p core level spectra in Figure 5e show a binding energy of 711.2 eV with a satellite structure at 716–722 eV, typical for Fe³⁺ in agreement with our Mössbauer spectra⁵¹. The O1s spectra in Figure 5f were fitted into two peaks at 530.2 eV and 531.5 eV, corresponding to metal-oxide bonds and defect sites with low oxygen coordination, respectively^{19, 45}. The defect sites with low oxygen coordination to metal-oxide ratios are 0.45, 0.29, and 0.22 for HEOFe, LiHFeF, and LiHFeCl, respectively, indicating that adding lithium, chloride, and fluoride reduces defect sites, with the lowest value for LiHFeCl. Figures 5g and 5h show the binding energies of F1s (686.0 eV) and Cl2p (198.0 eV),

respectively, corresponding to metal-fluoride and metal-chloride bonds^{19, 52}.

3.2 Electrochemical properties

The electrochemical performance of HEOFe, LiHFeF, and LiHFeCl in the 2032-coin cells was evaluated by cyclic voltammetry of Li insertion in the potential window of 0.65 V/3.0 V vs. Li⁺/Li at the scan rate of 50, 20, 10, 5, 2, 1, 0.5, 0.2 and 0.1 mV s⁻¹ and by galvanostatic chronopotentiometry at 1C. In addition, each cell was evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy after cyclic voltammetry and then after 50, and 100 cycles of galvanostatic charging/discharging. Figure 6a shows the cyclic voltammograms of HEOFe, LiHFeF, and LiHFeCl. All three cyclic voltammograms contain one reduction and one main oxidation peak at 1.0 V and 1.7 V, respectively. The charge capacities calculated from the oxidation branch of the cyclic voltammogram are 450, 694, and 593 mAh g⁻¹ for HEOFe, LiHFeF, and LiHFeCl, respectively. Such a high charging capacity speaks for a conversion reaction of lithiation for all three high entropy compounds with spinel structure, although the conversion mechanism is mainly suggested for the high entropy compounds with the rock salt structure with less space for Li accommodation³.

Figure 5. a) Cyclic voltammograms measured on the 2032-coin cells containing LiHFeOFeCl, LiHFeOFeF, and HFeOFe with a scan rate of 0.1 mV s^{-1} . b) The scan-rate dependence of the charge capacities calculated from the discharge branch of the cyclic voltammogram on the scan rate for HFeOFe (blue triangles), LiHFeOFeCl (brown squares), and LiHFeOFeF (green circles).

Figure 6b shows the dependence of the charge capacity calculated from the discharge (oxidation) branch of the cyclic voltammogram on the scan rate. The corresponding cyclic voltammograms are presented in Figure S2. Whereas LiHFeOFeCl already reaches its maximum charge capacity at the scan rate of 0.5 mV s^{-1} , the charge capacities of both HFeOFe and LiHFeOFeF exhibit a gradual increase with the decreasing scan rate, which evidences a slower conversion reaction. This effect is most probably caused by different particle sizes of tested materials. The lithiation mechanism of high-entropy oxides is a complex process involving a conversion reaction between divalent metals in the structure with Li^3 . This conversion reaction can be accelerated by increasing the interfacial area where the reaction occurs. Consequently, smaller particles with a higher surface-to-volume ratio are beneficial in promoting this process. Although the average crystallite size, D of HFeOFe is slightly smaller than that of LiHFeOFeCl (140 nm vs. 155 nm) (Figure 2), the size distribution of the latter exhibits its maximum for the particles with less than 100 nm in diameter. On the contrary, the maximum of the HFeOFe particle size distribution lies between 100 and 200 nm.

After cyclic voltammetry, the electrochemical impedance spectrum of a particular coin cell was measured. Then the performance of all three materials during long-term cycling was evaluated by galvanostatic chronopotentiometry at the 1C charging/discharging rate. In addition, the electrochemical impedance spectrum was measured after the 50th and 100th cycles of charging/discharging. Figure 7 shows the course of the galvanostatic curve for all three materials together with the calculated coulombic efficiency. Due to the interruption of galvanostatic measurements for all samples after the 50th cycle, (for electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurement), the coulombic efficiency curves show a small discontinuity. All the materials exhibit charge capacity decay, which is most

pronounced for LiHFeOFeCl. This capacity decay is typical for conversion electrode materials, which often show substantial capacity degradation at high currents due to kinetic limitations of the diffusion-driven processes during de-lithiation³.

The charge capacity is stabilized after 50 cycles at ca. 200 mAh g^{-1} for all the materials. Since the battery capacity decay is commonly accompanied by irreversible changes in the electrode materials, Raman spectroelectrochemistry on the LiHFeOFeF sample (with the most uniform particle size distribution) was measured to reveal morphology changes during charging/discharging. The coin cell equipped with a glass window near the LiHFeOFeF electrode was assembled for the in-situ Raman spectroelectrochemistry. The coin cell open circuit potential was 1.75 V before measurement. Chronoamperometry was applied to the freshly prepared coin cell in the potential range from 3 V to 0.7 V vs Li^+/Li . Figure 8 shows the Raman spectra of the electrode material recorded for each potential step during the lithiation (Fig. 9a) or de-lithiation (Fig. 9b). The reference Raman spectra of pristine LiHFeOFeF and carbon C65 are also shown in Figure 8a (red line) and 9b (blue line), respectively. The Raman features of LiHFeOFeF disappear during electrochemical charging and only the carbon additive C65 and electrolyte are seen at a potential of 0.7 V (Figure 8a). These data indicate that the structural disruption and changes of LiHFeOFeF during charging are not associated with any new Raman modes. Figure S3 (Supporting Info) shows current fluctuations occurring in the potential range around 2 V-1.6 V. These fluctuations are associated with the disappearing and rediscovery of Raman features of the LiHFeOFeF during charging at the discussed potential range (Fig. 9a). This behavior can be attributed to the first cycle on a freshly prepared electrode, where the electrode response is inhomogeneous, and the solid/electrolyte interphase is formed. The discharging process from 0.7 V to 3 V leads to gradual recovery of the LiHFeOFeF

Figure 6. Galvanostatic chronopotentiometry at 1C rate for HEOFe (blue circles), LiHEOFcCl (brown circles), and LiHEOFcF (green circles). The charge capacity within charging is marked with full circles and the charging capacity within discharging with empty circles. The corresponding coulombic efficiencies for HEOFe, LiHEOFcCl, and LiHEOFcF are depicted by squares of the same color coding.

Raman features (Fig. 9b). The spectra at 2 V and 2.8 V in Fig. 9b were collected at two different places of the cathode. The different rate of discharging in different places at an electrode is observed. Besides the inhomogeneity of the amount of LiHEOFcF material, the reason for this different recovery rate can be the different particle sizes in both places (see particle size distribution in Figure 2). However, the spectrum at 3 V is taken in the identical place of the cathode as the spectrum at 2.8 V and the LiHEOFcF Raman features recovery is confirmed. The data show good reversibility of the system during the first charging/discharging cycle.

The impedance spectra shown in Figure 9 confirm the high electrochemical activity of freshly assembled cells with LiHEOFcCl-based cathode. For easy comparison of individual electrodes, the spectra are normalized to the mass of active material³³. The EIS fitting provided the charge-transfer resistances of 5.36 m Ω ·g, 33.1 m Ω ·g, and 3.36 m Ω ·g for the cells with HEOFe, LiHEOFcF and LiHEOFcCl, respectively. Galvanostatic cycling causes a decrease of R_{CT} of both high-entropy oxyhalides, which is reminiscent of the similar behavior of LiHEOFcCl-based cathode in an electrolyte standardly used for Li-sulfur cells (LiTFSI + LiNO₃ in 1,3 dioxolane/1,2-dimethoxyethane)²³. In contrast, the cycling of HEOFe leads to a small enhancement of R_{CT} , which is accompanied by a marked improvement of the serial resistance, R_s . At this stage of our research, we have no persuasive explanation for the difference. The mechanism of electrochemical reduction of HEOFe and the high entropy oxyhalides can be different, which is mirrored in the specific EIS features of the former. Furthermore, the

extraordinary electrochemical activity of LiHEOFcCl, observed at early stages of voltammetric and galvanostatic cycling (Figs 6, 7, 8) is in accord with the smallest observed charge-transfer resistance of this particular material.

Figure 7. In situ Raman spectroelectrochemistry of coin cell with LiHFeOFeF cathode and 1M LiClO₄ in ethylene carbonate/dimethyl carbonate (1:1 by volume) as the electrolyte solution. (a) Charging of the coin cell from 3 V to 0.7 V vs. Li⁺/Li. The Raman spectrum of blank LiHFeOFeF is also shown (red line). The label rep stands for repeated measurement at 1.8 V. (b) Discharging of coin cell from 0.7 V to 3 V vs. Li⁺/Li. The Raman spectrum of blank C65 additive is also shown (blue line). Spectra are offset, but the intensity scale is identical for all plots.

Figure 8. Electrochemical impedance spectra of our coin cells with LiHFeOFeX- and HFeOFe-based cathodes. (A) Freshly assembled cells after nine formatting cycles by cyclic voltammetry. (Inset: details of the spectra measured at the high-frequency cutoff. (B) The spectra as in chart A but fitted to the equivalent circuit shown. (C) Spectra of the same cell after 50 galvanostatic charge/discharge cycles at 1C. (D) Ditto after 100 galvanostatic charge/discharge cycles at 1C. For color coding of curves see annotation in chart A. (E, F) Impedance spectra for freshly assembled and cycled cells (as in charts A-D, but with HFeOFe-based cathode).

Conclusions

The phase pure high entropy oxide $(\text{Zn}_{0.25}\text{Mg}_{0.25}\text{Co}_{0.25}\text{Cu}_{0.25})\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (HEOFe), lithiated oxyfluoride $\text{Li}_{0.5}(\text{Zn}_{0.25}\text{Mg}_{0.25}\text{Co}_{0.25}\text{Cu}_{0.25})_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_{3.5}\text{F}_{0.5}$ (LiHEOFeF), and lithiated oxychloride $\text{Li}_{0.5}(\text{Zn}_{0.25}\text{Mg}_{0.25}\text{Co}_{0.25}\text{Cu}_{0.25})_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_{3.5}\text{Cl}_{0.5}$ (LiHEOFeCl) were prepared by combination of mechanical milling and heat treatment. X-ray powder diffraction confirmed their spinel-based cubic structure ($Fd\bar{3}m$) with an average crystallite size of 50–70 nm. The corresponding particle sizes from (S)TEM are 3–4 times larger due to the agglomeration of the crystallites. EDS mapping confirmed a homogeneous distribution of constituent elements in all the prepared samples. In addition, the average elemental composition determined by AAS is close to the nominal composition. Mössbauer spectroscopy revealed that Li and F or Cl ions do not influence the redistribution of Fe^{3+} cations. Photoelectron spectroscopy provided deeper insight into the oxidation states of particular cations and anions.

Electrochemical measurements carried out in the 2032-coin cell with Li-metal anode indicated the voltammetric charge capacities of 450, 694, and 593 mAh g^{-1} for HEOFe, LiHEOFeCl, and LiHEOFeF, respectively. They exceed almost four times the theoretical capacity of classical intercalation cathodes of Li-ion batteries. The best electrochemical performance of LiHEOFeCl was ascribed to its smallest particle size enabling faster electrochemical conversion reaction. Galvanostatic chronopotentiometry at 1 C rate confirmed high initial charge capacities for all the samples but a capacity decay over 100 charging/discharging cycles. This decay was the most pronounced for the sample LiHEOFeCl with the highest initial charge capacity.

Raman spectroelectrochemistry of LiHEOFeF proved the reversibility of the electrochemical process for the initial charging/discharging cycles. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy data agree with cyclic voltammetry and galvanostatic chronopotentiometry for all three samples. The initial charge transfer resistance of LiHEOFeCl exhibits the lowest value and decreases gradually during galvanostatic cycling, analogously to that of LiHEOFeF. On the contrary, the galvanostatic cycling causes an enhancement of the charge transfer resistance of the HEOFe sample, obviously due to different mechanism of the electrochemical reduction.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, M.Z., L. K., and M. F.; methodology, M.Z., M. F., and L.K.; investigation, M.Z., M. F., O. P., L. K., B. P. L., V.Š., H.K., K.L.S., and M.L., data curation, M. Z., M. F., O. P., B. P. L., H.K., and L. K.; writing—original draft preparation, M. Z., L. K., and M. F.; writing—review and editing, M. Z., L. K., M. F., B. P. L.; project administration, M. Z., M. F.; funding acquisition, M. Z., M. F., H.K., O.P., and V.Š.. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability

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